

SUSTAINABLE CONSTRUCTION THROUGH RECLAIMED STEEL COMPONENTS: IMPLEMENTATION AND DEMONSTRATION IN THE DRASTIC EU PROJECT

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Abstract

The European building sector is a significant contributor to global greenhouse gas emissions, with embodied emissions in construction materials, particularly steel, playing a critical role. As European policies shift towards energy-efficient buildings, the focus on reducing embodied carbon has intensified. This paper examines the application of reclaimed steel components in new construction as a strategy to reduce embodied carbon, improve life-cycle performance, and support the circular economy. The study focuses on the development of a Demonstrator within the DRASTIC EU project, aimed at implementing innovative solutions for reducing both operational and embodied carbon emissions in steel construction by reusing steel from the Litoral de Almería Thermal Power Plant to construct a new warehouse in Balaguer (North-East of Spain). The paper outlines the process of reclaiming, inspecting, testing, and reusing steel components according to the latest European standards, emphasizing the role of traceability and advanced structural assessments. This initiative will highlight the potential of steel reuse in achieving significant sustainability goals in construction, offering a replicable model for future projects across Europe.

1 INTRODUCTION

The building and construction sector in Europe plays a major role in the quest towards sustainable development due to its high levels of embodied and operational Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions, which can be estimated around 40% of the worldwide emissions [1]. Furthermore, embodied GHG is considered to contribute between 10-20% to the total EU's building GHG footprint, depending on factors such as building type, construction technique, and materials. In 2019, the European Commission presented *The European Green Deal* [2], a roadmap for making the EU's economy sustainable by turning climate and environmental challenges into opportunities across all policy areas, and making the transition just and inclusive for all. As part of this roadmap, several research projects and standardization committees have been put forward at different levels to tackle this challenge.

In this framework, reclaiming and reusing structural components during renovation, retrofitting and new construction of buildings is considered a key strategy to reduce the embodied energy and carbon, increase the high-life cycle performance, and reduce life-cycle costs, making it therefore more affordable for a wider and diverse group

of building owners and users, which is especially suitable for steel structures. Although this is a wide field of research, this paper will focus on the application of this strategy to the development and construction of a steel warehouse from reclaimed components, a pilot project that will demonstrate innovative solutions to reduce operational and embodied carbon emissions while promoting the reclamation and reuse of materials. It is part of the DRASTIC EU project "Demonstrating real and affordable sustainable building solutions with top-level whole life cycle performance and improved circularity" (2023-2027), and it will follow the main standard recommendations [1,3].

2 EU PROJECTS RELATED TO STEEL REUSE

In recent years, several projects have focused on assessing the environmental impact of steel and composite buildings. For example, the EU-RFCS funded LVS3 project *Large Valorisation on Sustainability of Steel Structures* (2013-2014) developed and validated life-cycle methodologies for steel structures, offering a comprehensive set of resources, including background documents, a design guide, and user-friendly software. Another important initiative, the EU PROGRESS project "*Provisions for a Greater Reuse of Steel Structures*" (2017-2020), aimed to promote the reuse

of steel components in buildings by developing methods and protocols for both deconstructing existing buildings and designing new ones for future reuse. This project emphasized on the circular economy of steel construction, covering primary and secondary structures and hybrid components [4]. Building on PROGRESS, the ADVANCE project “*Accompanying measure for dissemination, valorisation and collaborative exploitation of circularity of constructional steel products*” (2023-2025) continues to address the challenges in the reuse of existing steel buildings and the design of new structures with enhanced reusability.

Finally, the DRASTIC project seeks to reduce the carbon footprint and enhance circularity in the European construction sector. By focusing on material reuse, innovative construction techniques and lifecycle performance, DRASTIC aims to create replicable models (Demonstrators) for reducing greenhouse gas emissions in both new and retrofit building projects. Figure 1 presents the work package (WP) structure and interactions of the Project, to show that the Demonstrators (WP3) play a central role in the total concept and structure of DRASTIC.

Figure 1: DRASTIC WP structure and interactions

3 EU STANDARDIZATION: CURRENT STATUS

The potential for reusing steel has been recognized for years, gaining prominence with the rise of sustainability and circular economy principles. Research in the early 21st century focused on key aspects like disassembly systems, storage, marking systems and the evaluation of the behaviour and structural safety of recovered elements, which led to the development of guidelines and recommendations that now underpin the new normative codes in this field.

In response to the European Commission’s Mandate M/515, specific Working Groups and Ad Hoc Groups were established to amend existing Eurocodes, broadening their scope to include sustainability requirements. As a result, the Technical Committee CEN/TC 135 recently published the Final Draft FprCEN/TS 1090-201 [5], which outlines the requirements for using reclaimed structural steel components in structures designed according to the EN 1993 series and executed according to EN 1090-2 [6], but limited to quasi-static loading without fatigue.

In addition, the CEN/TC250 committee formed the Working Group WG2 to develop rules for assessing and retrofitting existing structures, complementing EN 1990 and EN 1991. One key outcome of this WG has been the Technical Specification FprCEN/TS 17440 [7], which offers additional provisions to apply EN 1990-2 [8] to existing structures.

In the future, amendments to each Eurocode will include an Annex recommending modifications to account for existing structures and the use of reclaimed components. For steel structures, this work is being carried out by the CEN/TC250/SC3 Ad Hoc Groups, focusing on the assessment and retrofitting of existing iron and steel structures, and the design with reclaimed steel components for reuse. These groups are currently finalizing the “Guidance on Establishing European Design Rules for Re-Used Steel Components” [3], a Technical Report based on prior research and expert input. This guidance will be crucial in integrating reuse principles into the Eurocodes and ensuring a safe and sustainable reuse of steel components.

4 PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT & DEMONSTRATOR

4.1 General description

The DRASTIC project aims to develop, demonstrate and validate innovative and affordable construction solutions that reduce environmental impacts and enhance circularity significantly. The demonstration is carried out by developing solutions that focus on reuse and multi-cycle traceability, and integrating reclaimed and bio-based materials. Implementing these at full building scale (i.e., Demonstrators) in five European countries, including Spain, the Project seeks to accelerate the transition from a linear to a circular economy in construction, with ongoing performance measurements for future optimization.

The DRASTIC Spanish demonstrator focuses on the reuse of steel components with a special emphasis on enforcing traceability and the circularity of the steel construction sector. The Process Chain (PC) for the successful reuse of steel components, which will be used in the Spanish demonstrator, is described in detail in [1], and features the main aspects for confidently designing reused steel components according to Eurocode 3.

4.2 DRASTIC Spanish demonstrator

The Spanish demonstrator focuses on the reuse of the steel members reclaimed from the Litoral de Almería Thermal Power Plant (South-East of Spain) to build a new small steel warehouse in Balaguer (North-East of Spain), proving the feasibility of selective deconstruction and reuse of structural steel elements. The proposal is led by CELSA Group, and the value chain actors and stakeholders contributing to the demonstrator are SORIGUE, LEZAMA, ADEC, GBCE and UPC, which will provide the expertise on the structural performance and reliability of the reclaimed elements and resulting structure.

The specific steps towards the successful implementation of the Demonstrator within the context of the Process Chain proposed in [1] are described in the following sections.

Step 1 – Reclaim: Deconstruction & Preparation

The first step is to perform a thorough analysis of the information available on the donor structure in the form of reports, original drawings and onsite visits (see Figures 2 and 3) for demolition/dismantling provided by the deconstruction company, as well as the estimation, if possible, of the prior loading history of the elements and connections. This is followed by a detailed inventory of the elements to be reused and the study of the suitability of the different demolition alternatives available, following the rules and recommendations in [5]. In this particular case, the structure is a small 14.5×6 m warehouse built in 2017 by Enel Engineering & Construction–Endesa, with an average height of 3.4 m, and made from HEB140 columns and IPE240 and IPE180 beams using S275JR steel.

Figure 2: Donor structure: Drawings

Figure 3: Donor structure: Visual Inspection

Step 2 – Component Survey: Inspection & Testing

The proposed circular alternatives should be compared with the *Business as Usual* solutions, and assist the decision-making process. The development of the solutions includes the design, choice of materials and formulation, and the development of new or extension of existing quality control protocols to ensure the performance of products containing recovered elements and reusable elements. In order to be able to have a good traceability of all the components, a pre-

dismantling labelling was carried out on all recovered products (see Figures 4 and 5). The labels will be scanned and connected to the traceability platform to incorporate the results into the BIM building model, and later, the results of the quality control and labelling of the new solutions will be connected to the traceability platform for each Demonstrator.

Figure 4: Marking/labelling drawings

Figure 5: Marking/labelling process and result

Step 3 – Component Assessment & Classification

The component assessment is being carried out according to the rules of FprCEN/TS 17440 [7] and EN 1990-2 [8], and depends on the information available from the donor structure according to the principles described in [1]. Based on that, the most suitable characterization tests (measurement of residual and initial stresses, evaluation of fatigue and brittle fracture performance, measurement of geometric imperfections, section loss due to corrosion and characterization of mechanical properties) and structural behaviour tests on elements (beams and columns) will be performed at the LATEM Laboratory at UPC.

Steps 4 & 5 – Stockage & Market Placing

Once the pre-demolition study and labelling system were finished, the structure was carefully deconstructed (see Figure 6) and a stockage system of the steel components has been developed, which uses the information and classification system defined in the previous steps for the digital books. Likewise, ensuring that the degradation of the components (e.g., due to corrosion) does not occur and maintaining the mechanical safety for a future Market placing are key features of the stockage procedure.

Figure 6: Selective Dismantling Process

Steps 6 & 7 – Design & Structural Modification

The design of the new structure (the Demonstrator) will be performed using the measurements obtained in Step 3, and through advanced finite element modelling calibrated from the experimental tests (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Design of the new structure with reused elements

Parallel to this, a numerical parametric data generation will be carried out to assess the influence of the variability observed in the input characteristics (i.e., imperfections, initial stresses, mechanical properties) on the capacity of steel beams and columns. The procedure will allow evaluating the suitability of the prescribed partial safety factors γ_{M0} and γ_{M1} for a reliable reuse of steel components, comparing them with the recommendations set out in [4].

Step 8 – Construction, Installation & Future Optimization

Once the previous Steps have been completed, the Demonstrator will be constructed and installed using the reclaimed components according to the relevant specifications, and all the information will be implemented in the DRASTIC Digital Building Logbook.

After the installation of the new structure is finalized, its technical performance for further optimisation and future exploitation will be evaluated and measured to prospect the scaling potential of the solution by developing advanced finite element models in ABAQUS. Inputting measured mechanical characteristics, initial stress states and initial geometric imperfections, the numerical model will allow to assess the capacity of the new structure in the Ultimate and Serviceability Limit States, providing a benchmark reference for future monitoring and maintenance. Finally, a full structural reliability assessment will be carried out at system level using FORM techniques to propose alternative factors for system-based design using advanced analysis.

5 CONCLUSIONS

By successfully reclaiming and repurposing steel members from an existing structure (donor structure), the ongoing DRASTIC project will demonstrate the viability and environmental benefits of reusing steel components in new construction, reducing the embodied carbon footprint of the new structure significantly. The thorough process of inspection, testing, and structural assessment, guided by the latest European standards, will also ensure that reused materials meet all the necessary safety and performance requirements. This pilot Project will not only underscore the importance of circular economy principles in the construction sector, but will also provide a scalable model that can be applied across Europe. Once finalized, the Project will prove that the adoption of similar strategies can contribute substantially to the EU's sustainability goals, reducing both operational and embodied emissions while promoting material circularity.

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